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Characterisation of Fusion Quality between Filaments by FDM using Essential Work of Fracture

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- **Introduction**
 - Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM)
 - Motivation
- **Principles of Essential Work of Fracture (EWF)**
- **EWF of 3D printed polymer composites**
 - Materials: Pure nylon film, 3DP Nylon, 3DP Onyx
 - Effects of notch sharpness
- **Results & discussion**
- **Conclusion**

Definition: A material extrusion process used to make thermoplastic parts through heated extrusion and deposition of materials layer by layer. (ASTM – F2792 – 12a)

Question

Why was there a loss of mechanical properties in materials fabricated by FDM, compared with the feedstock material? ^[1]

Reasons

- Insufficient **fusion bonding**
 - Interdiffusion of polymer chains
 - Interlayer crystallization
- Presence of voids
- Structural anisotropic
- Poor interfaces (for composites)

How

EWF { Single-layer specimens: exclude interaction between layers
Reveal actual process-structure-property relationships between filaments

Double edge notch tension (DENT) test ^[2]

- Specimen is loaded in tension with load & displacement recorded
- The ligament (L) yields and crack propagates across L giving complete failure

Total energy dissipated during the DENT test is:

$$W_f = \int_0^{\delta_c} P d\delta$$

And it can be divided into two parts, i.e. the essential work in tearing the ligament ($w_e BL$) and the plastic work ($\beta w_p BL^2$), i.e.

$$W_f = w_e BL + \beta w_p BL^2$$

Hence $w_f = \frac{W_f}{BL} = w_e + \beta w_p L$

Therefore, specific work of fracture (w_f) is plotted against ligament length (L), the positive intercept of the straight line would be the specific essential work of fracture (w_e)

Tested 3 types of materials

- Pure nylon film (traditionally manufactured)
- 3DP Nylon
- 3DP Onyx* } 3D printed

FTIR results & DSC confirm the **chemical similarity**

Effects of **notch sharpness** were also studied (laser VS **razor**)

Pure nylon

3DP Nylon

Fracture behavior:

- “self-similar” load – displacement curves
- Typical ductile polymer
- DENT specimens notched by laser absorb more energy – due to blunt crack tips

w_e of Pure Nylon Film

- $w_{e, \text{laser}} \gg w_{e, \text{razor}}$
- Good correlation (R^2) – **0.94** VS **0.95**
- Similar value of w_e found from literature
- **30.3 kJ/m^2** – benchmark

Fracture behavior:

- Curves – with consistent trend
- For batch notched by laser – load keeps increasing after complete ligament yielding
- Sensitive to notch sharpness

- $w_{e, \text{pure nylon}} > w_{e, \text{3DP Nylon}}$
- Both are sensitive to notch sharpness

Short fibre reinforced nylon

$V_f \approx 15 \%$

Orientated along printing path
predominantly (due to the shear
flow)

Effects of addition of short carbon fibres?

	w_e (kJ/m ²)
Pure nylon film (laser)	73.3
Pure nylon film (razor)	30.3
3DP Nylon (laser)	43.0
3DP Nylon (razor)	22.8
3DP Onyx (laser)	27.6
3DP Onyx (razor)	29.9

Onyx – short CFR nylon

- $w_{e, \text{laser}} < w_{e, \text{razor}}$
- Scatter – R^2 : **0.75 VS 0.64**
- Little effects of notch sharpness
- Enhanced toughness
- Still lower than pure nylon made by traditional method

Fracture Surface of 3DP Onyx

- Fibres are orientated perpendicular to load direction predominantly
- Relatively poor fibre-matrix interfaces

- Propose and investigate a feasible and practical method to characterize fusion quality of 3DP polymer composites – conduct **DENT** tests to determine the specific essential work of fracture (w_e)
- Blunt notch tips by laser result in a much higher value of w_e than that by sharp razor blade for neat nylon; while SCFR nylon is found to be less sensitive to notch sharpness
- Lower values of w_e of 3DP nylon were found compared to that of pure nylon film made by traditional method – intrinsic to the FDM process?
- Inclusion of short fibre does help improve the fusion quality, but not significantly – orientation + interface

Thank you!

